

HISTORIC PLACES OF BUKHARA

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Abstract: this article gives the information about some historic places of Bukhara. The influences and the importance of these historical monuments on culture and technology are also discussed in this article.

Key words: mosques, madrasah, bazaar, palace, culture, tombs, manuscripts, architecture

Bukhara is one of the oldest and largest cities Central Asia, which has been playing for many centuries an important role in the history of society and has repeatedly been the capital of the states that were formed on territory of Uzbekistan. Century after century many generations and people of Bukhara contributed to the construction of the city, became a "Museum City". Bukhara is one of the few cities in the world that has been developing since the 5th century BC and grew up in the same place. History of Bukhara its roots go back to hoary antiquity. According to archaeological excavations, its age is 2500 years, this date was celebrated in 1997.

Bukhara is a truly unique world of architecture, the world is so whole, despite different styles, currents, era that it is difficult to give preference to any one mosque. There are few cities in the world where so many diverse and multi-temporal monuments of material culture and art, like Bukhara. City occupies one of the prominent places in terms of the wealth of architectural monuments – masterpieces architects of the East. Majestic monuments of art and culture attracts close attention not only of specialists and tourists, but also of ordinary people. Because these masterpieces were created by the ancestors of the same people. From generation to generation passes on the unique experience of masters of architecture, culture and applied arts. Priceless experiences and traditions are usually passed on through hard work of young students. Here the primary role belongs to labor education. A higher level of this process acquires a cultural the nature of learning. Historical cultural monuments of Bukhara in the areas of influence and technology performances are divided into the following groups:

1. Architectural monuments (palaces, mosques, madrasahs, minarets, caravanserais, tims, toki - chorsu, bazaars, sardoba, ponds, fortresses - estates,

housing architecture).¹

2. Objects of applied art (items of jewelers, blacksmiths, potters, tanners, weavers, etc.);
3. Monuments of fine art (miniatures, sculpture, decoration premises);
4. Monuments of writing (examples of calligraphy, manuscript, books, inscription on dishes, architecture and tomb inscriptions);
5. Household items (tools, household and auxiliary items);
6. Weapons and means of protection (spear, sabers, blades, battle axes, chain mail, cavalry armor);
7. Numismatic materials (ancient Sogdian, Ephthalite, Turkish, Chinese, Caliphate, Samanid, Karakhanid, Mongolian, Timurid, Sheibanid, Ashtarkhanid, Emirati coins).²

All these cultural monuments have a specific basis of influence in the process education of the younger generation. Each group of them has its own unique educational potential. It lies in the art of creating this masterpiece. Here the work and art of the master harmoniously coincide with the taste requirements of the young people of all generations. Because of this, they are uniquely original. It is one of the best examples of well-preserved Islamic cities of Central Asia of the 10th to 17th centuries, with an urban fabric that has remained largely intact. Several prominent people lived in Bukhara in the past. Most famous of them are: Muhammad Ibn Ismail Ibn Ibrahim Ibn al-Mughirah Ibn Bardiziyeh al-Bukhari (810-870); Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) - physician and person of encyclopedic knowledge; Balyami and Narshakhi (10th century) - the outstanding historians; al-Utobi (11th century); Ismatallah Bukhari (1365-1426) - the illustrious poet; Mualan Abd al-Khakim (16 century) - the renowned physician; Karri Rakhmatallah Bukhari (died in 1893) - the specialist in study of literature; Mirza Abd al-Aziz Bukhari (the end the 18th century - the beginning of the 19th century) - the calligrapher.

Bukhara was long an important economic and cultural center in Central Asia. The ancient Persian city served as a major center of Islamic culture for many centuries and became a major cultural center of the Caliphate in the 8th century. Bukhara is one of the oldest cities in Central Asia. Its history is connected with the Arabs and the Mongols, who at various times owned this territory. The

¹ Muminov Kh., Muzaffarov A. Bukhara region. Tashkent. Uzbekistan, p135-151, 1976.

² Muminov Kh., Muzaffarov A. Bukhara region. Tashkent. Uzbekistan, p 50-55, 1976.

location of the city can be called strategic, so it was often subjected to invasions. The Silk Trade Route passed through the city, which helped in the development and strengthening of ties. There was little crime in Bukhara of the past, so almost no prisons were built. Only one zindan has survived to this day - a real fortress. The architectural ensembles of the district were sometimes formed over the centuries, but they look like a single whole. Each ruler wanted to leave a legacy behind, so new mosques, madrasahs, minarets and tombs appeared regularly. Some of them have retained their functions, while others have become museums. In 1991, Bukhara was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. In 1997, under the leadership UNESCO on an international scale widely celebrated the 2500th anniversary of the city. In Bukhara to this day preserved ancient architectural monuments. On theits territory contains monuments of all historical epochs from the 2nd to the 19th–20th centuries.

In the XII century, under the command of Arslan Khan, the city was completely rebuilt. Among other things, the ruler conceived the creation of the Poi-Kalyan complex. The minaret appeared at the same time, and the current cathedral mosque and Miri Arab madrasah - only in the 16th century. The place was not chosen by chance: in the past there was already a mosque here. At the time of the creation of the project, only ruins remained from it. The new building accommodated about 12 thousand people for simultaneous prayer. According to this indicator, it became the second in the country. The minaret is over 46 meters high. It has never been renovated. The madrasah is still used for its intended purpose. The Silk Trade Route passed through Bukhara. For this reason, they traded willingly and a lot here. At the intersection of roads, domed buildings were erected - something like covered bazaars, called "currents". Markets of different directions united under one roof. Traditionally, four currents are distinguished: Toki Sarrafon, Toki Telpak Furushon, Tim Abdulla Khan, Toki Zargaron. You can buy everything from jewelry to old books.

Mausoleum of the Samanids is located on the site of an ancient cemetery, which was revered in the past. It was erected in the 9th century in the traditional Sogdian style, but with the use of more durable materials. The external features of the building refer to the vision of the creators of the world. At the base is a square - a symbol of the earth, and crowned with a dome - the vault of heaven. Three theologians are buried in the mausoleum, including the founder of the Samanid dynasty.

In the central part of Bukhara there is Lyabi-Hauz square. Around it is a complex of old buildings. The development of this area was carried out in the XVI-XVII centuries. Kukeldash Madrasah was the first to be built. It combined a mosque,

residential areas and classrooms. And Nodir-Divan-Begi initially served as a caravanserai, therefore it is devoid of many features familiar to a madrasah. Hanaka Divan-Begi is small in size, but it has a rich finish. A full-fledged component of the complex is a fountain. During its history, it managed to visit a pond, a water reservoir, and also, after draining, a sports ground.

Sitorai Mohi-hosa- the palace was built at the beginning of the last century. It served as the country residence of the Emir of Bukhara. Although the complex was characterized by a European style, inside there was a division into male and female halves. Currently, the museum of decorative and applied arts is located inside. It has been operating since 1927 and has been seriously updated several times. One of the most popular expositions is the interiors of the palace.

Ark is the oldest archaeological site in Bukhara. The construction was carried out in the 10th century, but the earliest surviving buildings inside the walls date back to the 17th century. Legends attribute the founding of the fortress to the local hero Siyavush. Omar Khayyam also lived here for some time. The unique library did not survive due to regular wars and attacks on the citadel. Now the architectural and art museum is based here.

Chor-Bakr was originally located in the village, but the territory was later included in the city. The history of their dynasty dates back to Muhammad himself. The necropolis was created to preserve the unique tombs. Over several centuries, the district was gradually overgrown with buildings, and the entrance was made in the form of an original gate. The last burials date back to the beginning of the last century.

Mausoleum of Chashma-Ayub- the name is translated from Persian as “the source of Job”. There is a spring near the tomb. According to legend, he appeared thanks to the prophet Job: with his staff, he touched the ground to give water to the locals. Although the mausoleum was built in the 12th century, there are no burials from that period. The building was rebuilt many times, including under Tamerlane. Now inside there is a water museum and an exhibition of carpets.

Bukhara is one of the centers of the medieval culture of Central Asia. Bukhara is a truly unique world of architecture, the world is so integral, despite different styles, currents, eras, that it is difficult to give up preference for one particular mosque or minaret located in center of the Silk Road, Bukhara connected many countries of the East and West. In Bukhara, architectural and historical monuments passed down from generation to generation, erected many years before our era, have been preserved in their original form, which attract attention numerous visitors to the city.

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